

A Simple Analytical Derivation of the Lyapunov Exponent for the Logistic Map at $r = 4$ Without Trigonometric Substitution

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Abstract

We present a simple and transparent analytical method for computing the Lyapunov exponent of the logistic map at $r=4$. Instead of using the classical invariant measure, we take the logarithm of the product of the derivative and an auxiliary function, which reduces the computation to three well-known elementary logarithmic integrals that precisely cancel each other out. Additionally, we demonstrate that the Lyapunov exponent for the period-1 orbit (unstable fixed point $x=3/4$) takes exactly the same value as that for the fully chaotic attractor ($\lambda = \ln 2$). This result highlights the consistency between local instability and global chaotic divergence, and the proposed method serves as an accessible pedagogical tool for introducing deterministic chaos at the undergraduate level.

Keywords: Lyapunov exponent, logistic map, chaos, fixed point

1. Introduction

It is well known from the scientific literature that the logistic map [1]

$$x_{k+1} = rx_k(1 - x_k) = f(x_k) \quad (1)$$

can generate orbits with various periods, including chaotic ones. The particular case $r=4$ is especially interesting, as the system exhibits fully developed deterministic chaos, with the variable x densely filling the entire attractor interval $0 < x < 1$ [1,2].

One of the key quantitative indicators of dynamical behavior is the Lyapunov exponent. A positive value of this exponent is a hallmark of chaos. In general, the Lyapunov exponent is defined as the long-time average of the logarithm of the absolute value of the derivative along a typical trajectory [3,4]:

$$\lambda = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \ln |f'(x_k)| \quad (2)$$

In practice, this formula is most commonly used for numerical computations.

For the special case $r=4$, an analytical expression for the Lyapunov exponent is also known, based on the invariant measure [2,5]:

$$\lambda = \int_0^1 \ln|f'(x)| \rho(x) dx \quad (3)$$

where

$$\rho(x) = \frac{1}{\pi\sqrt{x(1-x)}} \quad (4)$$

is the invariant density of the logistic map at $r = 4$ [2,5,6].

Substituting (4) into (3) and performing appropriate analytical transformations – often involving a trigonometric substitution – yields the well-known result $\lambda = \ln 2$ [5-7]. Although this method is correct, its analytical evaluation is not particularly straightforward for pedagogical purposes.

2. Simple Method with Auxiliary Function $g(x)$

In this note we propose a considerably simpler approach to deriving the Lyapunov exponent analytically. We start from the following expression:

$$\lambda = \int_0^1 \ln[|f'(x)|g(x)] dx \quad (5)$$

where the auxiliary function is given by

$$g(x) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x(1-x)}} \quad (6)$$

In this formulation, the logarithm is taken of the full product $|f'(x)|g(x)$, and the factor π appearing in the classical invariant measure (4) is replaced by 2. This form turns out to be much more convenient for direct computation and leads to elementary integrals.

Substituting (6) into (5) and using $f'(x) = 4(1 - 2x)$, we obtain

$$\lambda = \int_0^1 \ln\left(\frac{4|1-2x|}{2\sqrt{x(1-x)}}\right) dx = \ln 2 + \int_0^1 \ln\left(\frac{|1-2x|}{\sqrt{x(1-x)}}\right) dx = \ln 2 + R. \quad (7)$$

It is straightforward to show that the residual integral vanishes exactly:

$$\begin{aligned}
R &= \int_0^1 \left(\ln|1-2x| - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\ln x - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\ln(1-x) \right) dx = \\
&= -1 - \frac{1}{2}(-1) - \frac{1}{2}(-1) = -1 + 0 = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where we have used the standard results. This immediately gives $\lambda = \ln 2$.

3. Lyapunov Exponent of the Period-1 Orbit Compared to Chaos

It is worth noting another interesting feature of the dynamics at $r=4$: the Lyapunov exponent of the period-1 orbit (fixed point) has exactly the same value as that of the fully chaotic attractor.

The fixed point satisfies

$$x_s = \frac{r-1}{r} = \frac{3}{4} \tag{9}$$

The derivative at this point is

$$f'(x_s) = 4(1-2x) = -2 \tag{10}$$

which immediately gives

$$\lambda = \ln|f'(x_s)| = \ln 2 \tag{11}$$

Thus, the local rate of divergence of nearby trajectories near the unstable fixed point matches the average rate of divergence along typical chaotic orbits. This equivalence is a noteworthy and instructive property of fully developed chaos at $r=4$, illustrating how the strongest local stretching rate determines the average divergence along chaotic orbits [4–7].

References

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